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The aphid *Sitobion avenae* (Hemiptera: Aphididae): A new record from rice fields at Edfina, Beheria Governorate, Egypt

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Abstract

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Rice is a very important cereal food crop in Egypt, coming second after wheat. The current study was carried out at Edfina rice fields for three seasons, 2023: 2024, and 2025. *Sitobion avenae* (Fabricius) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) was observed occurring, for the first time, on rice plants at the Edfina location, Beheria Governorate, in 2022. Continuous monitoring revealed that *S. avenae* was found at very low levels at the beginning of the season up to mid-August. The population densities were highest throughout September up to mid-October (44.25-81.06 nymphs and adults/10 rice hills), then the aphid densities were low by the end of the season. Compared to Giza 177, Sakha 104, and Sakha 108 varieties, Super 300 rice variety was the most susceptible to *S. avenae* (58.68 and 108.30 nymphs and adults/10 rice hills) in the first and second seasons, respectively. Two insect predators, *Coccinella undecimpunctata* (L.) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) and *Reduvius pallipes* Klog (Hemiptera: Reduviidae), were associated with *S. avenae*. It was found that the *S. avenae* population correlated positively and significantly (0.6639 and 0.7417) with the *C. undecimpunctata* population and *R. pallipes* with values of 0.8422 and 0.8493 in the first and second seasons, respectively. It could be concluded that *S. avenae* is an emerging insect pest in rice fields. This may be the first record of the insect in Egypt. Despite the infestations being low, except for the Super 300 rice variety, it is important to intensify the insect monitoring of the aphid on rice fields, particularly with dramatic changes in the global climate. In the 2025 season, the insect was observed to be infesting on different rice varieties.

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa*) is one of the most important food crops worldwide. In Egypt, rice comes second, after wheat, as an important food crop. Rice

cultivation faces several biotic and abiotic challenges. Insect pests, such as the aphid *Sitobion avenae* (Fabricius) (Hemiptera: Aphididae), damage leaves and panicles. Nagrare

(2012) and Fallahzadeh *et al.* (2014) reported that *S. avenae* attacks a wide variety of plant species, including vegetables, field crops, and wheat, causing yield reductions. *S. avenae* is one of the piercing sucking insects that negatively impact wheat plants around the world (Gaston and Lawton, 1988, and Irshad, 2001). When the aphids attack wheat spikes during the flowering stage, yield could be reduced by about 15% (Oerke, 2006, and Taheri *et al.*, 2010). Feeding of aphids on leaves and buds of wheat plants may cause severe damage to the wheat production (Khaliq, 2003).

Late-planted wheat is at risk of the grain aphid infestation, especially if the temperature remains cool until the end of March (Bhambhro, 2002). Early sown wheat varieties have a low incidence of aphid infestation, but late sown ones have a high aphid infestation, which negatively affects wheat production (Riazuddin *et al.*, 2024). The reproduction rate of aphids is affected by temperature, which is the most important abiotic factor affecting the physiological functions of aphids (Chakravarty and Gautam, 2004). Despite the short life cycle of aphids, insect metabolism increases with rising temperatures, leading to the production of more dispersed individuals (Drake, 1994).

In a choice test, the rice root aphid *Rhopalosiphum rufiabdominalis* (Sasaki) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) was fed on variable graminaceous hosts. Rye and wild rye were the most preferred hosts, followed by wheat, barley, and oats, while rice and sorghum were poor hosts, and corn was non-host (Anonymous, 2004). In addition to direct damage caused by sap sucking, due to their feeding on plants, aphid species can transmit viral diseases from diseased plants to

healthy ones. In this regard, RDPV (Rice dwarf polerovirus) can be transmitted by aphids and whiteflies, and the viral-diseased rice plants suffer from stunted growth stress (Yu *et al.*, 2024).

Plants respond to aphid attacks by different mechanisms. Guerrieri and Digilio (2008) explained this reaction by direct resistance through activating defense genes and by indirect resistance through releasing specific volatile compounds that attract natural enemies to aphid-infested plants. Fortunately, crop fields are rich in several species of predators that can regulate aphid populations to less than economic injury levels (Macfadyen *et al.*, 2018, and Wang *et al.*, 2019).

The current study aimed to monitor the population dynamics of the aphid *S. avenae*, which has been recently found infesting rice plants at Edfina District, Beheira Governorate. At the location, the susceptibility of four commonly cultivated rice varieties to the aphid was estimated. Population dynamics of two predators associated with *S. avenae* were considered. In addition, correlation coefficient values between aphid population and each of the predators, *Coccinella undecimpunctata* (L.) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) and *Reduvius pallipes* Klogwere (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) were computed.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental site:

This experiment was conducted at rice fields in Edfina District, Beheira Governorate, Egypt, during the 2023 and 2024 summer seasons. The objective was to investigate the rice varieties' infestation by the aphid at the location. This is because the authors have observed that some rice hills were found infested by aphids in the 2022 summer season. As the

authors are aware, the literature did not indicate any rice infestations by such insect pest in Egypt.

2. Common cultivated rice varieties at the location:

Rice varieties sown at the location were Giza-177, Sakha-104, Sakha-108, and Super-300. The varieties were sown in nurseries by the third week of June, and their seedlings were transplanted one month later. Each variety occupied an area of 1000 m², which was divided by borders into four equal sections (Replicates). At transplanting, rice seedlings were pulled out and distributed in the plots in a completely randomized block (CRB) design, with four replicates for each variety. Thus, the experimental area comprised 16 plots (four varieties, four replicates).

3. Population dynamics of the aphid and its associated predators:

The population dynamics of the aphid *S. avenae* F. (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and two associated predators, *C. undecimpunctata* and *R. spallipes*, were visually monitored. The numbers of the aphid (Nymphs and adults), *C. undecimpunctata* (L.) (larvae and adults), and *R. pallipes* (Nymphs and adults) were monitored and recorded/10 rice hills/plot at each sampling date from the beginning of August up to the 30th of October. Both the nursery and paddy fields have not received any pesticides throughout the course of study in the 2023 and 2024 seasons.

4. Aphid identification:

Aphid specimens were sent to the “Department of Survey and Classification of Insects” at the Egyptian Reference Museum, Plant

Protection Research Institute, Dokki, Cairo, for identification.

5. Statistical analysis:

The MSTATC statistical software was used to calculate ANOVA among rice variables (Freed, 1991). Duncan’s Multiple Range test (1955) was computed to compare means at a significant level of 5% (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Results and discussion

1. Nature of aphid infestation on rice plants:

Aphid infestation was observed on some rice leaves for the 2022 summer season. As the authors are aware, there are no publications on aphid infestation on rice plants. Monitoring the spots of infestation in rice fields sown with the Super 300 rice variety revealed that the aphids (Nymphs and adults) spread to the panicles and different parts of rice plants (Figures 1 and 2).

2. Aphid identification:

Specimens of aphids were identified by taxonomists at the “Department of Survey and Classification of Insects” at the Egyptian Reference Museum, Plant Protection Research Institute, Dokki, Cairo, as the aphid, *S. avenae*, collected from infested rice plants, preserved in vials having alcohol 70% with a few drops of glycerin. As the authors are aware, no aphid infestation in rice plants has been previously recorded. However, Nagrare (2012) and Fallahzadeh *et al.* (2014) reported that *S. avenae* attacks a wide variety of plant species, including vegetables, field crops, and wheat, causing yield reductions in 2001.

Figure (1): A colony of the aphid *Sitobion avenae* on rice leaves.

Figure (2): A colony of the aphid *Sitobion avenae*, on rice florets and panicles.

3. Population dynamics of aphids on rice plants:

3.1. In the 2023 season:

The aphids were not detected regardless of the rice in mid-August on all rice varieties. However, for the varieties, the population density of the aphids increased gradually to reach 18.88 nymphs and adults/10 rice hills. The highest population densities were detected throughout September, ranging between 44.25 and 81.06

nymphs and adults/10 rice hills. The densities were also high during the first half of October and decreased to 19.88 individuals /10 rice hills on the 30th of October.

3.2. In the 2024 season:

As in the first season, no aphids were attained up to mid-August. However, the population densities of the aphids remained low from August 22nd (8.88 aphids/10 rice hills) up to September 11th (14.44 individuals).

The duration from September 18th to October 13th witnessed the highest aphid population densities, with values ranging between 46.69 and 64.75 nymphs and adults/10 rice hills. Both Bhambhro (2002) and Riazuddin *et al.* (2024) concluded that late sown wheat is at risk of the grain aphid infestation, especially if the temperature remains cool until the end. The reproduction and survival of aphids are highly affected by temperature, which is the most important abiotic factor affecting physiological functions of aphids (Chakravarty and Gautam, 2004). Despite the short life cycle of aphids, insect metabolism increases with

rising temperatures, leading to the production of more dispersed individuals (Drake, 1994).

4. Susceptibility of rice varies to aphid infestation:

4.1. In the 2023 season:

The four evaluated rice varieties differed significantly in their reaction to rice aphid *S. avenae* infestation (Table 1). The least infested variety was Giza 177 rice variety (12.02 nymphs and adults), followed by Sakha 104 variety (18.95) and Sakha 108 variety (20.93). However, the most infested variety was Super 300, which had 108.30 aphid nymphs and adults/10 rice hills.

Table (1): Population dynamics of the aphid *Sitobion avenae*, on rice varieties at Edfina, Beheira Governorate, 2023 season.

Date of Examination	Av No of aphids/10 rice hills				Average \pm SE
	Giza 177	Sakha 104	Sakha 108	Super 300	
Aug. 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00
7	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00
14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00
21	7.00	19.25	2.75	19.25	12.06 \pm 4.24
25	5.00	19.00	5.00	44.75	18.44 \pm 9.73
Sept. 1	17.25	22.25	17.25	119.25	44.25 \pm 25.02
7	16.75	50.50	15.25	175.50	63.75 \pm 38.22
14	16.25	60.25	60.25	185.25	80.50 \pm 36.42
20	37.25	48.25	15.50	223.25	81.06 \pm 47.88
30	13.25	12.50	97.00	161.00	76.94 \pm 35.98
Oct. 7	19.25	7.50	25.50	248.25	75.13 \pm 57.82
14	15.25	14.00	31.75	156.50	54.38 \pm 34.28
21	16.00	7.50	14.00	122.75	40.06 \pm 27.62
30	4.50	4.25	8.25	60.50	19.38 \pm 13.74
Average \pm SE	12.02 \pm 2.73 c	18.95 \pm 5.35 B	20.93 \pm 7.29 b	108.30 \pm 23.22 A	

4.2. In the 2024 season:

Similar to the first season, Giza 177 rice variety appeared less preferred to aphid infestation, with 12.36 nymphs and adults/10 rice hills (Table 2). The second and third ranks of rice susceptibility to aphid infestation

were occupied by Sakha 104 and Sakha 108 with 14.43 and 22.77 nymphs and adults/10 rice hills, respectively. Also, Super 300 rice variety exhibited the highest susceptibility to *S. avenae* (58.68 nymphs and adults/10 rice hills).

Table (2): Population dynamics of the aphid, *Sitobion avenae*, on rice varieties at Edfina, Beheira Governorate, 2024 season.

Date of Examination	Av No of aphids/10 rice hills				Average ± SE
	Giza 177	Sakha 104	Sakha 108	Super 300	
Aug. 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00
22	6.50	14.00	3.50	11.50	8.88±2.38
29	7.50	16.50	6.75	16.50	11.81±2.71
Sept. 4	11.50	11.50	6.75	11.50	10.31±1.19
11	8.25	16.00	16.50	16.50	14.44±2.06
18	14.50	31.50	106.50	106.50	64.75±24.35
26	49.75	46.00	11.25	144.25	62.94±28.61
30	16.00	25.25	104.00	104.00	62.31±24.14
Oct. 6	15.75	16.75	16.75	158.75	52.00±35.58
13	24.55	11.00	25.75	125.75	45.69±26.56
20	14.25	7.00	5.75	75.75	25.69±16.79
27	4.75	6.00	15.25	50.50	19.13±10.72
Average ± SE	12.36±3.45 c	14.43±3.47 Bc	22.77±6.56 b	58.68±15.72 a	

In case of wheat infestation with aphids during the flowering stage, yield could be reduced by about 15% (Oerke, 2006, and Taheri *et al.*, 2010). In the same trend, Khaliq (2003) clarified that the feeding of aphids on leaves and buds of wheat plants may cause severe damage to wheat production. In the 2025 season, the aphid was continuously monitored and found slightly infesting rice varieties, but with a relatively high infestation of the Super 300 rice variety.

5. Insect predators associated with the aphid *Sitobion avenae* in rice fields:

Data presented in Tables (3 and 4) show that two insect predators were considered in the current study as associated with *S. avenae* in rice fields. These predators were found as *C. undecimpunctata* and *R. pallipes* correlated positively with *S. avenae* with values of 0.6639 and 0.7417, and *R. pallipes* also correlated with positive values of 0.8422 and 0.4893 with *S. avenae* populations in the first and second seasons, respectively.

Table (3): Population dynamics of the aphid, *Sitobion avenae*, and associated predators on rice plants at Edfina District, Beheira Governorate, 2023 season.

Date of Examination	Av No of aphids/10 rice hills		
	<i>Sitobion avenae</i>	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i>	<i>Reduvius pallipes</i>
Aug. 1	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	1.00	0.00
21	12.06	2.75	0.00
25	18.44	3.00	1.75
Sept. 1	44.25	2.75	1.25
7	63.75	2.00	1.75
14	80.50	2.50	1.75
20	81.06	4.00	2.25
30	70.94	3.25	1.50
Oct. 7	75.13	3.50	2.00
14	54.38	3.25	0.75
21	40.06	2.50	0.50
30	19.38	3.25	0.75
Correlation Coefficient Values Between Aphids and Predators		0.6639	0.8422

Table (4): Population dynamics of the aphid, *Sitobion avenae*, and associated predators on rice plants at Edfina District, Beheira Governorate, 2024 season.

Date of Examination	Av No of aphids/10 rice hills		
	<i>Sitobion avenae</i>	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i>	<i>Reduvius pallipes</i>
Aug. 1	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	0.00	1.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.25	0.00
21	8.88	1.50	0.00
25	11.81	3.50	1.25
Sept. 1	10.31	3.75	1.50
7	14.44	4.50	2.25
14	64.75	3.25	3.00
20	62.94	5.25	2.50
30	62.31	8.00	2.25
Oct. 7	52.00	4.25	2.75
14	46.69	4.50	1.75
21	25.69	4.50	1.75
30	19.13	3.25	0.75
Correlation Coefficient Values Between Aphids and Predators		0.7417	0.8493

Aphid feeding on plant hosts releases specific volatile compounds that attract natural enemies to aphid-infested plants. Fortunately, crop fields are rich in several species of predators that can regulate aphid populations to less than economic injury levels (Macfadyen *et al.*, 2018, and Wang *et al.*, 2019).

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